

Unfurling the Literary Appreciation Strategies Utilized by Secondary Male Teachers

Allan John T. Alcala

Abstract. Reading offers an exploration of the past, an appreciation of the present, and a glimpse of the future. Literary appreciation helps students acquire and develop sensitivity, self-awareness, and a greater understanding of the world and other people. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the study unfurled the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights regarding the literary appreciation of teachers. The participants of the study were ten (10) male secondary teachers currently teaching in a secondary school belonging to the first district of Davao City. Extracted narratives from the interview revealed teachers' experiences in literary appreciation, such as biases on male English teachers, lack of learning resources, and students with different levels of language proficiency. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms of the teachers were resourcing strategy, repeat reading or rereading, and finally, reading between the lines. However, teaching literature does not have a one-plan-fits-all dictum. From these findings, insights were drawn. Employing innovative learning tasks will promote students' interest and engagement in learning literature, while teachers becoming role models will influence students to become avid readers and develop skills valuable in their educational journey.

KEY WORDS

1. secondary male teachers 2. literary appreciation 3. coping mechanism

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1. Introduction

Literature involves different skills from plain reading comprehension text, and one of the skills in literary comprehension is literary appreciation. The satisfaction and delight in reading literature emerge from engaging with themes and topics that are interesting to the readers. Since it deals with scenarios, feelings, things, and ideas that the reader can either enter into imaginatively or constitute part of the reader's experience, they can relate the literary texts they are reading to their own lives (Abida, 2016). According to Mallikarjun (2003), studying literature for its intrinsic merit and enjoyment is a powerful educational tool that imbues values, language style, and many other opportunities for learning into the learners' minds. Teaching literature can motivate and interest when teachers employ appropriate learning strategies in the classroom. Research claims that teachers' teaching strategies affect students' achievement, and it is assumed that learners will feel motivated to participate actively in the teaching-learning process. These employed strategies will be the learners' guide

in reaching their optimal competence in learning (Magulod, 2018). Reconsidering the methodologies employed by the teachers in teaching literature is as equally important as the content of the literature instruction. The mundane teaching techniques of the English teachers and language instructors in literature class demotivate learners to appreciate the beauty of literature, and it often fails to attract the student's attentiveness and fascination towards literary texts. In Malaysia, the National Education Blueprint 2013-2025 revealed that the mode of instruction of almost half of the local teachers is lecture only (Rawian, Yahaya, Sanjaya, and Abdullah, 2022). Hwang and Embi (2007) observed that most teachers repetitively use three activities in literature instruction. The first is reading the text, then rereading and paraphrasing the text to recall important details, and the last is asking questions taken from the textbook to determine whether the learner understands the literary text. Using these activities repeatedly can create a monotonous classroom that reduces the motivation of the students to learn. Additionally, Kow (2007) stated that some teachers employ repeated reading as an effectual teaching tool in inducting understanding and appreciation of literature. Amateur and inexpert teachers are oblivious that their techniques may "assassinate" a literary text. According to Omar (2017), one of the reasons behind these issues is the teachers' inadequate knowledge about instructional approaches that underpin the use of literature in the English language. Paran (2008) reiterated that if teachers are less informed about effective teaching practices may significantly decrease the success rate of the learners' English proficiency and literary appreciation. However, the lack of sufficient time to cover the entire syllabus in English due to the literature component is what makes the instructors worried. As a result, teachers usually utilize the "chalk and talk" technique (Isa and Mahmud, 2012). Inevitably, the teacher will dominate the teaching-learning process leaving the students very limited chances to actively participate in the discussion (Basree, 2009). With this, any means of getting the students' attention and interest in learning literature might be derailed. The students will be uninterested in the lesson and they will also fail to appreciate literature as a whole. It is also important to note that a teacher's attitude and perception towards teaching literature play a vital factor in motivating the students to learn the lesson (Thamrini Syed, 2018). The lack of indulgence in literary texts among learners would eventually hinder the pleasure of reading and writing (Sivasubramaniam, 2006). In connection with this, a lot of learners continually fail to deeply understand the intention of the author in the literary text they are reading (Omar, 2017). Furthermore, culturally and contextually unfamiliar literary texts can cause the learners to be bored with reading and will be reluctant to meaningfully engage with such literary texts (Radzuwan, Malachi and Shireena, 2010). Bustamante (2022) stated that no single strategy will fit all the learners in teaching literature. One strategy might inspire the other students but might also cause some frustration. In this sense, he suggested that teachers should prepare a lesson plan that is well-crafted and carefully planned, rich with varied strategies that will satisfy the interests and needs of all learners. Parojenog (2020) said the same thing. According to him, some teachers are having difficulty fitting their approaches to various teaching techniques, particularly in teaching literature. Similarly, it is imperative for teachers to understand the different learning styles of their students to match their learning methods to the learners' learning interests and needs. For students to have a literary appreciation, teachers need to develop and choose appropriate strategies to apply during their class discussions and activities to ensure the students' quality of learning. According to Simene (2014), many students find literature boring and very tough. This perception of the

students in literature will hinder them from appreciating the beauty of literature, which will eventually result in an intellectual problem. Using varied teaching strategies that cater to the individual needs of the teachers will help them develop literary appreciation. In that way, students will be able to better understand the text they are reading, enjoy every word written in the text, and find a connection to their own lives. In the City of Davao, particularly in District 1, it has been observed that teachers handling literature subjects have difficulty teaching their students literary appreciation. Oftentimes, they utilize activities that students usually find boring and repetitive, decreasing their motivation to learn. Effective and meaningful literary instruction will help learners develop an appreciation of the different literary texts. The success of this goal lies in the teachers' competency and efficiency in employing strategies for teaching lit-

erary appreciation. The strategies, approaches, and techniques they will employ in the classroom will affect the motivation of the students to learn, understand, and appreciate literary texts. Most studies conducted in the international and national context are dominated by female teachers as participants since there are more female teachers handling English subjects compared to males. It is in this premise that this study is conceptualized. This study determines the strategies employed by secondary male English teachers in one of the secondary high schools in District 1, Davao City, and how they cope with the challenges as they develop their strategies in literary appreciation. The results of this study will contribute to its body of knowledge and improve the teachers' teaching quality in efficiently teaching literary appreciation to the students.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study was intended to explore the literary appreciation strategies employed by secondary male English teachers as well as how they cope with the challenges in developing strategies for literary appreciation. The demands of 21st-century learning in the teaching-learning process are to accommodate the needs and interests of the learners of the present generation. Employing appropriate strategies for a specific subject or course, such as literary appreciation, helps students to feel motivated and actively participate in the discussion. Through their experiences and strategies, information will be gathered in order to build up and formulate insights essential to adding to the existing body of knowledge about the teaching-learning process in literary appreciation. Most importantly, it will help the teachers to improve their teaching skills in helping the students to read beyond the text, develop their imagination and critical thinking skills, and appreciate the pieces of literature around the world.

1.2. Research Questions—The purpose of this study lies in its aim to explore the literary appreciation strategies of secondary male English teachers as well as how they cope with the challenges in developing the said strategies. This study will be conducted to seek and provide answers to the following questions:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of secondary male English teachers regarding literary appreciation?
- (2) How do they cope with the challenges in developing literary appreciation strategies?
- (3) What education management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Literary apprecia-

tion. It is reading, understanding, and critically judging the theme, style, use of figurative and non-figurative language, and other elements of

a literary work. Resourcing Strategy. It refers to the act of utilizing other sources to support one's understanding of a literary piece. This can include using a dictionary and the internet. Elab-

1.4. Significant of the Study—Putting into consideration this cited problem situation and the research questions, the researcher finds it timely to propose this study. This also brought the necessity for the researcher to unfurl the experiences of male English teachers as well as strategies for the achievement of literary appreciation. The researcher hopes that this study will be beneficial to the identified sectors of the academe. This includes the educational leaders, the school heads/school principals, learners, other stakeholders, and future researchers. The educational leaders. Educational leaders would benefit from the findings of this study because this can provide them with perspective on how to address the experiences of male English teachers. It can also provide them with

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on the Reflectivism Theory of Jerome Bruner (1960). Reflectivism is not different from constructivism. It is also embedded in constructivism, and it extends constructivism a bit further. Reflection refers to a process in which experience is recalled and all information regarding the situation is considered and evaluated in order to arrive at a decision. Reflection involves critical thinking about past or current experiences in the classroom. It involves questions regarding what was good or bad, what worked or did not work, what motivated students and the like that affects teaching and learning (Robinson, 2015). The strategies utilized by male teachers for literary appreciation are subjected to reflection if those strategies worked in favor of the students. If the strategies utilized

oration. It is the linking of ideas contained in new information or integrating new ideas with general information.

strategies and insights to enrich and improve the learning delivery in order to achieve literary appreciation. The school heads/school principals. The findings of this study might help school heads or school principals be aware of the teachers' experiences regarding literary appreciation. They can also devise ways to help the teachers achieve their goals regarding literary appreciation and provide support. The learners. The learners may see the real-life impact and benefits that come with learning and appreciating literature. Other stakeholders. They may provide support to enhance better the teaching-learning experience in teaching and achieving literary appreciation. The future researchers. This would be helpful and an additional contribution to their references for future research in the field of literary appreciation.

helped the students formulate a profound understanding of the literary pieces. Teachers and students work cooperatively to effectuate meaningful learning. The activities require learners to obtain knowledge through processes namely inquiry, interpretation, and creation. Gordon (2009) believes that knowledge is derived from integrating thinking and doing, and from reflecting on what was done. He added that he also maintains that learning, mental development, and knowledge are embedded in a particular social and cultural context when learners work with peers under teacher supervision. Reflectivism would be utilized in this study by unfurling the strategies utilized by male teachers for literary appreciation and determining whether they were deemed useful for the students' reading comprehension. Through it, they will be

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

able to reflect on the teaching strategies they employed, whether they bring about significant changes to the students, and whether they need to be improved and enhanced. The study was further reinforced by Constructivism Theory by Lev Vygotsky (1978). As a proponent, he claims that social interaction and social context are essential for cognitive development. Constructivism is based on the belief that learners work to create, interpret, and reorganize knowledge. Learners participate actively to reconcile the information they receive in the classroom with their existing knowledge, within the cultural and social contexts in which the ideas occur. Learners interact with people who are more knowledgeable than they are to increase their knowledge. These people include the teacher and the more knowledgeable students. In lit-

erary appreciation, teachers guide learners to create meaningful learning and a profound understanding of literary appreciation. Through these, students will be able to read beyond the lines. It will also help them be active in the learning process. Teachers are the ones equipping the students to become the best versions of themselves, acquire as many skills as they need, and hone them in becoming lifelong learners while being responsible for their own learning and taking active participation in the learning process. Constructivism deals more with learning, while reflectivism is more about teaching. Through inquiry, reflectivism brings about flexibility in teaching by helping the teacher examine the successes and failures in facilitating the learner’s knowledge construction.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitates the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon

for these people?” The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to unfold the strategies employed by secondary male teachers in teaching literary appreciation and how they cope with the challenges they face in developing these strategies. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested the information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the coming conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research – selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an act of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimates,” or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the strategies employed by secondary male English teachers in literary appreciation and how they cope with the challenges are discussed by the participants and tries to look into how they cope in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant’s answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. I upheld the authenticity of the responses and prevented them from making personal biases as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants on the epistemological assumption. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2006), I identified phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. This study intended to gather information from the participants or the secondary male English teachers from Sta. Ana National High School is based on the DepEd Division of Dava protocol. It was assured that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the strategies used by secondary male English teachers in teaching literary appreciation as well as how they cope with the challenges that they faced in developing these strategies. Axiology. It refers to

the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) argued that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. The researcher ensured the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpreted them in light of the participants' in-

terpretations. Rhetoric. It means reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it meant that the research would report objectively on what was observed and heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definitions. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the strategies employed by secondary male English teachers in literary appreciation as they shared how they cope with the challenges they faced in developing these strategies.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method. The methodology was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, secondary male English teachers from Sta employed literary appreciation strategies. Ana National High School was gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD), and their ways of coping with the challenges were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the strategies employed by the secondary male English teachers in teaching literary appreciation and how they cope with the challenges in developing the strategies became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the experiences and strategies of secondary male English teachers in literary appreciation and how they cope with the challenges in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the

experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey and Higgs (2006), experience refers to a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). This research, by delving into the experiences and coping strategies of secondary male English teachers, not only contributes to the field of education but also provides valuable insights into the nature of teaching and learning. By doing phenomenology, which concerns the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 2000), the researcher projected that the strategies and how they cope with the challenges used by secondary male English teachers were explored, and educational management insights gained were the basis for possible future research and policy analysis in relation to this research.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research, specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, were also used. The data were read and reread and were culled for phrases and themes that were grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, I was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with its roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, I used bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing was taking notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell, (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews are also useful to follow up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their

subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees said (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information about a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that extracted significant statements from the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected for the study were individuals who had actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher also needed to decide how and when his or her personal observations should be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations

and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Since the focus of this study was to explore the secondary male English teachers' experiences in employing literary appreciation

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions would lead to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (1967) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to 25, and Morse (1994) suggests at least 6. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualita-

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations were significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues regarding the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations could be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher must adhere to promote the research aims imparting authentic knowledge, truth, and prevention of error. Social Value. The research was very essential to society. In this study, the social value was focused on the literary appreciation strategies of secondary male English teachers. This study was specifically conducted among secondary male English teachers in Sta. Ana National High School. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which sec-

strategies, how they cope with the challenges in developing these strategies and the educational insights gained from the findings of the study, the researcher intends to employ phenomenology as a type of qualitative method research.

Qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 1990). The participants of this study were Ten (10) male teachers from a secondary high school in the 1st district of Davao City. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: secondary male English teachers; currently teaching in Sta. Ana National High School; and currently handling a literature subject. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

ondary male English teachers handling literary subjects could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest of the researcher is the strategies employed by secondary male English teachers in teaching literary appreciation. Informed Consent. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to the participants ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature and was based on the understanding of adequate information. The recruitment and selection of participants are lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants

were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research. Vulnerability of Research Participants. This study's participants could answer the research instrument because they are all professional teachers in secondary high schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she could easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, in the event that respondents would experience potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher has ensured that the respondents were safe during the conduct of the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at their convenience. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this

was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their natural sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were given consideration so that there would be no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they must be completely honest in answering the survey questions. Additionally, any type of communication concerning the research should be done honestly. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results. Transparency. The results of the study were accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and was placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. In addition, by learning from the results of the study, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview was carried out. This provided the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information which they felt might identify them. I reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the participant's identity in all subsequent

data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. I ensured that he or she possessed the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should complete the academic requirements and pass the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. I should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully in the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher has a responsibility to uncover, transfer, and exploit knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher interviews the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing works of literature and related studies and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him demonstrate competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and em-

within the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. I respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else said his or her way. I also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data or results was included, or purposefully put forward conclusions that were not accurate.

ploying Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. I ensure different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and video recording. The recordings were transcribed verbatim before data analysis could begin. Records done by the researcher are appropriately secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, when the data were being collected, the researcher's primary responsibility was safeguarding participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Analyst of data. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher made sure that the findings were

true to the participants and that their voices were heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The findings of the study are presented, too, by research questions—stating the results for each

2.7. Data Collection—The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School. The researcher asked for an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges in the last week of April the year 2023, as one of the documents needed for submission to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in asking permission to conduct the study. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. In the first week of May 2023, the researcher asked permission from the school's division superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with the attached Chapters 1 and 2 together with the research instrument explaining the study's objectives and the participants' identification. As a researcher, I would wait for the SDS's response before conducting it. Asking for permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools in the third week of May 2023, explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. During the fourth week of May 2023, the researcher asked permission from the participants. They were formally

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the

one by using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for the improvement of educational policy and practices.

oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. In the same week, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. On the last week of May 2023, the researcher transcribed the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since some of the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data will then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative

analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes told a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. The researcher employed thematic content analysis to describe qualitative data. A detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In ad-

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: familiarization, identifying a thematic framework, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected that is interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field

dition, to enhance validity and create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher employed environmental triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study’s results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the information received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as the time, day, and season of the study. The idea was to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement as mentioned was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing-up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

notes) Moreover, it gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher will become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process—for example, the mixed methods used,

such as interviews, documents, and observations. The second stage, identifying a thematic framework, occurs after familiarization, when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues at this stage. The researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this. The key issues, concepts, and themes expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that could filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections corresponding to a particular theme. This process is applied to all textual data gathered, such as transcripts of interviews. For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer (1994) recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated

in the margin beside the text. Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994:186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations are reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness was significant because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it was being conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study was essential to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility was how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study’s findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (1985) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue is “how we ensure rigor in the research

process and how we communicate to others that we have done so.” Transferability is how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study’s findings apply to other contexts. In this case, “other contexts” could mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using a graphic organizer as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. Using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. The researcher is interested in the students’ perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide a generalization of the study based on his context and could be able to address the core issue of “how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory.” Confirmability was the degree of neutrality in the research study’s findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on partici-

Figure 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

pants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of the research participants' statements to fit a certain narrative. The information used in the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to

replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher used an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, using a database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected were adequately kept for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue that "the way in which a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the participants' responses. The secondary male English teachers unfurled their employed literary strategies for achieving literary appreciation.

3.1. The lived experiences of secondary male English teachers in literary appreciation— Literature is life, and teaching it can become motivating and engaging when the teacher utilizes appropriate teaching strategies in the classroom. It plays a significant part in a student's education in secondary school. By readily and fully

understanding literary pieces, they can gain profound understanding and literary appreciation. These benefits can go a long way as they read and grow as students. However, it will not be as smooth as a red-carpet ride. It is full of quests and challenges. The secondary male English teachers unfurled their experiences regarding literary appreciation.

3.1.1. Biases on male English teachers— As advanced and as developed as our society can be, there are still difficult to alter views. One of these is people's views regarding male teachers, specifically male English teachers. Based on the responses of the participants', teaching literature is usually perceived as a feminine activity. They narrated that students are more used to having female English teachers. In line with the participant's responses, Moosa and Bhana (2018) agreed with the perception that teaching

is "women's work" and reading is a feminine activity. Teaching is equated to childrearing and often falls solely to the mother or a female head of the household. This situation reflects historical and cultural factors that have contributed to the sustenance of a male provider role. Moreover, in both Australia and South Africa, the construction of teaching as women's work" has particularly damaging consequences for those men who do choose to teach young children. In both contexts, the plight of the male teacher

has become one in which their masculinity is policed, questioned, and scrutinized. Men who teach young children are frequently marginalized and may be automatically viewed as effeminate or labeled “gay” regardless of their masculinity or sexuality (Bhana Moosa, 2018). The discrimination that male teachers experience can be traced down to the history of their role and people’s perception of them in society. These ancient views are hard to get rid of no matter how modernized we can be. Helbing (2012) also believed that men are better performers in terms of visual tasks, while women are superior to men when it comes to verbal affairs. Although differences between men and women might be attributed to the differences in brain

3.1.2. Lack of learning resources—In order to hone the students to become avid readers, they need to have books or learning materials at hand. The availability of materials will encourage them to read and learn more. However, as narrated by the participants as one of their experiences, the achievement of literary appreciation is made harder by the lack of learning resources. These include textbooks and other reading materials. These factors hinder the teachers from encouraging their students to read because how will they develop a habit of reading when there are no resources? The Nigeria Education in Emergencies Working Group (2019) agrees with the participants. In the study they conducted, they also found out that there is a shortage of textbooks. This problem contributes greatly to the poor teaching and learning in schools in Nigeria. UNICEF (2017) further supported that the lack of qualified teachers, lack of textbooks, and other school supplies is also very common in many schools. Hence, the problem with the lack of learning resources is not foreign to us. It has been around but still not addressed. In order to deliver quality instruction, prescribed textbooks and functional libraries where students can access or lay hands

structures of men and women, it is also possible that in a classroom context, these differences stem from the fact that teachers with different genders tend to show different behaviors towards boys and girls. However, Dahiru (2020), saw this matter in a different way. According to him, in the world of education, where male teachers are perceived as more assertive in conveying lessons to students, while female teachers are known to be soft-spoken with a warm attitude in giving lectures to students. Both have their own unique way of delivering instruction. But one common denominator is that, whatever the gender of the teacher is, challenges are inevitable.

on the books should be provided. It is impossible to effectively deliver lessons and any genre of literature if the students do not have the books or if they have not read them. Moreover, Ugwu (2022) also believed that to effectively teach literature, it is essential that the students read the texts before the lesson so that the time is spent on discussing the lesson and not wasted on reading during class hours. Furthermore, if reading is to take place in the class, some of the students who do not have the texts will become passive listeners and it might be difficult for the teacher to sustain their attention during the whole period. The same problem was also observed by Zhen (2012) in China. According to her, among the four major problems in teaching literature that she observed, inadequate and inappropriate teaching and learning resources are some of them. Dahiru (2020) also found the same problem in his study conducted in Nigeria. According to the participants, there is a shortage of resources required to teach literature in all public secondary schools. They also added that it is very difficult for the school administration or parents to provide all the literary text for the students to read. To synthesize, the abovementioned studies supported the responses of partic-

ipants regarding the lack of learning resources. Books and other reading materials are a vital part of student's learning and achievement of literary appreciation.

3.1.3. Students' different levels of language proficiency—A classroom is composed of diverse students. Teachers are greeted with different personalities, learning styles, preferences, and levels of language proficiency. Based on the participants' answers, one experience that they also shared is the diversity of students. They have students who have different levels of language proficiency. This difference tends to bring challenges on the part of teachers and in teaching literary appreciation. The aforementioned theme of teachers' experiences finds support in the following studies. As Ugwu (2022) emphasized, in a country where English is not the first language, students find it hard to understand literary text written in a language other than their own. Their inability to read, write, copy notes, or even participate in class discussions will hinder the whole teaching-learning process. In literature subjects where reading is a pre-requisite skill, little can be done or achieved if students cannot read. It was further supported by Irene (2014) who states that it can be very difficult for teachers to teach literary texts if the language level of the text itself is higher compared to the level of the students. This problem requires the teachers to explain the text to the students word by word, and this method is very time-consuming. If the students find the text too difficult to understand, they will eventually become disinterested and when they become uninterested in the subject, their attitudes and motivation will become negative. The same problem was also revealed in the study of Novianti (2016) who stated that the huge gap between the students who have different levels of language proficiency creates an imbalance in the class. Students with high levels of language proficiency tend to dominate the class discussion while those who have a low level of language proficiency would become passive listeners unless the teacher encourages them to participate in the class discussion. The low-level students will eventually become uninterested in the discussion since they cannot comprehend all of the information during the discussion. The same study also revealed that teachers face this challenge because their students are not avid readers. Many students are not fond of reading, and as a result, some students go to class unprepared and do not read the assigned text or chapter to be discussed. This problem would make it difficult for teachers to effectively deliver the lessons because the students could not actively participate in the class discussion since they did not know the content of the literary text they were assigned to read. Figure 4 shows the experiences of male English teachers in literary appreciation and decision-making and the emergence of the three themes: Biases on male English teachers, Students with different levels of language proficiency, and Lack of learning resources.

3.2. The coping mechanisms of teachers for the challenges in developing a literary appreciation—

3.2.1. Engaging in resourcing strategy—One challenge that teachers face is the lack of learning materials. These learning materials are meant to be useful for the students to help them interpret literary pieces, but they are not available. This puts a lot of burden on the teacher. When students encounter difficult and unfamiliar words, it can hinder their understanding, and so it also hinders the achievement of literary appreciation. The extracted statements of the

Figure 3. The lived experiences of secondary male English teachers in literary appreciation

participants were supported by Huang and Es-lami (2013). They revealed that the ability to look up the meaning of unfamiliar terms improves in-depth comprehension of a specific text and the precision of the words in a given context. Literature learners must acquire a large vocabulary to understand the text's whole passage fully. McEwan (2022) further emphasized the role of teachers. They can guide students to make use of searching the internet and dictionaries to understand unfamiliar words found in the given literary piece for a better elaboration of the texts. This will enable the students to define words and terms and clarify misunderstandings so they can appreciate literature. Hamilton (2012), in his study, also concluded that the dictionary helps learners improve reading comprehension and leads to lexical improvement. When students understand the words they are reading, they are closer to the goal of appreciating the literary pieces given to them. Furthermore, since it is essential to understand unfamiliar words and interpret the overall meaning of a sentence, most of the vocabulary is gained through reading. According to Sadieda, Bimantoro, Muzakie, Bagus, and Rahmawati (2019), dictionaries can be helpful in reading because they help find out the meaning of unfamiliar words. Aside from utilizing online resources, teachers can also encourage

the students to bring and use dictionaries whenever discussing a literary piece. Meanwhile, with regard to online sources such as Google, as mentioned by one participant, Noor (2011) posits that online reading resources and electronic dictionaries are also popular among today's adult students. These can be beneficial in helping them grasp the reading material quickly. Because their vocabulary is restricted, second language learners struggle to grasp the material without using a dictionary. As an alternative tool in resourcing, an e-dictionary provides a quick lookup tool to help them understand what they are reading (Bakar, Noor, Azman, Nor and Hamat, 2011). As supported by Abdulmalik (2020) in their study, it was found that participants relied on using online dictionaries and translation applications regardless of their accuracy in identifying word meanings. Such applications are the Microsoft Word Thesaurus services which they use as their second option to look up word meanings. This supports the necessity of utilizing online sources to eradicate the problems students use in addressing words that are difficult to understand. Regarding the strategies in literary appreciation, resourcing could be a big help for students in understanding the whole text. It is a great mechanism that a teacher can use to guide and support students as they engage in literary appreciation.

3.2.2. Employing repeat reading—In order to grasp the meaning of a literary piece and to be able to truly appreciate it, one has to read it, at the very least, once. As one of the strategies employed by teachers for literary appreciation, it is a great help to promote a better understanding of students. As they narrated, it can be time-consuming. However, it will help them achieve the objective of understanding and appreciating a literary piece. Aligned with the strategy used by teachers, APL Marketing (2020) also stated that teachers often make the students read the

text repeatedly until it makes sense to them or until they can understand the message the text is trying to convey. Studies have shown that repetition is an important tool because it assists in transitioning skills from the conscious to the subconscious mind. By repetition, a skill is performed and rehearsed over time until it becomes easier for students to utilize it (APL Marketing, 2020). Studies demonstrate the favorable effects of repetitive reading on improving reading skills without considering reading disabilities (Dundar Akyol, 2014). This means that it has

positive benefits for students and is a proper coping mechanism that teachers utilize in developing literary appreciation. Rereading is the strategy wherein an ongoing and repeated encounter with a text is guided by a particular task so that text segments get revisited and rethought (Berg Lyke, 2012). When employed, this strategy helped students understand literary pieces, especially the ones with unfamiliar words. This allows the participants to develop a deep understanding of a book's plot or character development, which is impossible to read a literary piece just once. In addition to that, Fields (2019) added that with a structured, consistent focus on repeated reading, students might be more likely to increase their comprehension than without applying repeated reading. The repeated reading strategy is effective for typically developing students, students with disabilities, and English Language Learners. Moreover, (Berg and Lyke, 2012) indicated that repeated reading might also improve a student's ability to read and compre-

hend new, unfamiliar passages fluently. This implies that the repeated reading strategy helps students stop reading word for word and helps them read in larger chunks (Almutairi, 2018). When repeated reading is effectively utilized, students can learn to generalize the technique and increase comprehension in other content areas. Moreover, the study conducted by Dotson-Shupe (2017) found that repeat reading research affected comprehension. More precisely, the conducted pre-test/post-test indicated a beneficial change in scores for several participants. Most of the passages read for the second time improved in terms of accuracy, fluency, and time spent reading. Hence, the good outcomes of the study support the use of the approach of repetition in reading to increase comprehension success. Relative to the strategies in literary appreciation, repetition can be one of the practical tools in enhancing reading skills that could enable students in their literary appreciation.

3.2.3. *Reading between the lines*—To achieve literary appreciation, one must read between the lines. This could be done by having an in-depth reading of the text, leaving no words unturned, and noting idiomatic expressions and imagery used by the author. Based on the participants' answers, literary pieces bear meanings not easily grasped just by reading a text. One has to read between the lines. A study by Taki and Soghady (2013) reveals that different proficiency levels determine the strategies used in understanding idiomatic expressions. For learners to successfully decode the meanings of idioms, knowledge of the target culture must be integrated into language teaching and learning. Idioms are difficult to understand - particularly for non-native speakers because their meanings are usually metaphorical. The responses of the participants are in line with this view. Their concern of how hard it must be for students to

grasp the meaning of idioms and idiomatic expressions used in a piece. Since the students are non-English speakers, they will face a hard time understanding idioms. English as Second Language (ESL) learners will need to familiarize themselves with the meaning and usage of each idiom. Using common idioms and expressions will make ESL learners sound more native. Thus, it is a good idea to master some of these expressions. In the same thread of thought, according to Amos and Abas (2021), learning idioms is a challenging task, especially for non-native speakers of English. With the necessity to understand the underlying cultural influences that idioms are based on, ESL learners need to unearth their metaphorical connotation and relevance to the context of the text where it was presented. It implied that age is a factor in the comprehension of idioms among children. Therefore, exposure to language input is vital in

early acquisition. Conversely, the imagery does not revolve around the text itself but can also fuel be understanding between the lines. With relevance to imagery, Robinson (2019) stated that imagery is an act of employing words to generate images in the reader's mind and deeply understand what the writer implies to their readers. The abovementioned studies supported and

3.3. Insights Are Drawn From The Experiences And Challenges Of Secondary Male English Teachers In Literary Appreciation—In light of the findings of this study, literature offers students to learn other skills such as reading, writing, and speaking. It opens doors to skills and abilities that students can acquire. Meanwhile, teaching literature is not only concerned with teaching students how to make lit-

3.3.1. Employ innovative learning tasks—In our contemporary classroom setting, teachers face enormous challenges brought on by a complex and rapidly changing society. Participants mentioned that we are in the 21st century. This age requires a different set of skills and strategies for students to succeed. These innovative learning tasks for literary appreciation can include but are not limited to movie trailer making, movie poster making, character montage, jingle rap method, literary map activity, timeline method, character line interpretation, pick-up line making, and journal writing or blogging. Based on the participants' answers, these strategies are useful to keep the students engaged and motivated. In fact, studies relating to literary appreciation skills and innovative learning tasks of students have been conducted by numerous researchers. Bunsom, Singhasiri, and Vungthong (2011) found that employing literature-based learning activities in the classroom stemmed from the teacher's desire to see students read texts that are familiar to them in or-

agreed upon teachers' sentiments regarding imagers and idiomatic expressions. They have expressed how challenging it is for students, which is why noting idiomatic expressions and images is essential so the students can create an accurate interpretation and achieve a literary appreciation of the text given.

erary interpretations and analyses but also helps students acquire and develop sensitivity, self-awareness, and a greater understanding of the world and other people. The participants were asked about their insights, suggestions, or recommendations to better deliver the learning of literary appreciation to the students. A few of the participant's insights were carefully deciphered and noted.

der to stimulate their literary appreciation skills. Rita (2012) adhered to the benefit of innovative learning tasks. She investigated the effectiveness of innovative literary-based learning activities to improve the literary appreciation of students. Results showed that using such learning activities, students indicated a positive attitude toward literary appreciation. The appreciation conducted by the students makes them realize the importance of responding to literary works to develop character. In accordance with the above-cited studies, the focus is on the use of innovative learning tasks in enhancing students' literature appreciation and reading skills. Teaching literature can become motivating and interesting when appropriate teaching strategies are employed by the teacher in the classroom. Very often, teachers either lecture or use question-and-answer or recitation. Recitation is often not appropriate because the question remains at the level of who-what-when-where, but hardly ever how and why. Li (2011) noted that the teacher's job is to nourish and enhance students' intelli-

Figure 4. Coping mechanisms of teachers for the challenges in developing literary appreciation

gence. In the conventional approach to literature teaching, it is only focused on linguistic competence such as reading, recalling, and reciting literary works. Revisiting the literary appreciation skills of the students will make teachers become aware of the extent how they develop the literacy competence of their students. Such information will further provide measures on how to improve their teachings, particularly by using innovative learning tasks in their literature classroom. Teaching literature to students requires creativity, ingenuity, and innovativeness. It is through teaching literature that the literary appreciation skills of students are developed. Teachers must be able to design effective learning tasks to help learners learn literature in the

best possible ways. Ahmad (2009) over-claimed that in the process of developing students' literary appreciation, teachers El-Hilalay (2014) revealed that it becomes imperative to use innovative teaching strategies and techniques in literature teaching which are beneficial in enhancing the literary reading appreciation and performance of students. The modern concept of education requires a lot of innovations that should be introduced in the educational system thus, the opportunity to educate 21st-century individuals cannot be taken for granted by any academic enterprise for the quality of education it offers is measured by the quality of leadership manifested by the teachers (Magulod, 2017).

3.3.2. Teachers are role models—Figuratively speaking, teachers are like the main characters in the story. They play the most crucial part in the student's achievement of literary appreciation. Hence, the extracted statements from the responses of the participants unfurled that teachers should act as role models, as a learner of literature. That way, the students can imitate their ways and their attitude. Students should see that you, as a teacher, is eager to learn and teach a story at the same time. Lumpur (2015) adheres to the presented theme. Teachers are believed to be the link between learners and knowledge. Being the first ring of the chain in this process gives teachers the opportunity to be the facilitators of learning and the authority to enable students to increase their independent learning capabilities. To better enable learn-

ers to enjoy and appreciate literary texts and develop their capacity for critical thinking, creativity, and self-expression, teachers are encouraged to show the aforementioned characteristics as well. A teacher should set an example for the class. Research, such as that of Erdem (2015), has shown that the role of the teacher in the classroom is highly significant since he increases the achievement of foreign language learning. Teachers can be facilitators instead of mere lecturers or coaches by providing students with situations where they need to have different approaches and more practical examples. More importantly, teachers can set themselves as an example for the students. Teachers should also learn with the students, exhibit the ideal qualities of a good and wide reader, and keep an open mind for different perspectives and interpretations.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, I present a summary of the study. From the summary of the findings, I draw implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of secondary male English teachers as they dealt with the challenges surrounding the achievement of literary appreciation. To achieve the research objectives, I made

Figure 5. Insights drawn from the experiences and challenges of secondary male teachers in literary appreciation

use of a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which were the narratives of secondary male English teachers regarding literary appreciation. In light of the male English teachers' experiences, the first theme that was discovered from the study was the presence of biases against male English teachers. Based on the participant's narratives, being a teacher does not depend on gender. The focus should be on how the students are learning. Some may still have mixed perceptions upon seeing a male teacher, these things do not matter to them at all. Based on the participant's narratives, being a teacher does not depend on gender. The participants in the study are not fazed by these biases and challenges that are rooted in their gender. Instead, they are trying their best to prove that being an excellent teacher is not based on gender. The second theme was the lack of learning resources. Teachers also expressed that teaching literature is already hard, but it is so much harder when you are teaching it without ample resources. The problem of public schools regarding the availability and supply of books has been around for so long yet is still not acted upon by the authorities. This makes teaching literature harder because teachers need to find ways to provide students with copies of the piece that they will discuss. The third theme was the student's different levels of language proficiency. A diverse class is also one of the experiences of the participants. They are greeted by a variety of readers; some are advanced and get to the point in no time. There are also others who need more time, attention, and guidance. Meanwhile, with all these experiences and challenges, teachers have devised coping mechanisms. For the lack of resources, they have utilized a resourcing strategy. They encourage the students to look for other sources to aid their understanding. They hone students to become wise readers and to see opportunities in every challenge. Another coping mechanism employed by teachers is repeated reading. Although repeat reading or rereading can be perceived as time-consuming, it is deemed to be an effective strategy to ensure student understanding. Reading it once is not enough, especially when dealing with literature that requires in-depth and critical reading. This strategy is also made to cater to a diverse group of students, as stated by the participants in the interview. There was also reading between the lines. Similar to repeat reading, reading between the lines helps enrich the student's understanding of the literary piece. Teachers use this method to deal with the variety of students in their classes. The participants expressed that they do not want any of their students to feel left out. They want everyone to feel included in the discussion. Aside from that, as teachers, it is their greatest happiness to see their students learn and improve. The two insights drawn from the study were the innovative learning task and teachers becoming role models. The first insight, which is employing innovative learning tasks, is targeted towards improving learning delivery and enriching the way students learn. Considering that we are in the 21st century with learners who are digital natives, it is important that learning delivery and classroom instruction cope with the changes. That way, the needs of the students will be met while keeping their interest in the lesson, especially in literature class. At the end of the day, the students are at the top of the hierarchy, they are the priority. Their learning is the duty of a teacher. For them to learn, they need to be engaged and interested. Hence, the innovative learning task is one of the 'themes because teachers want to deepen and widen the learning experience of students, they will learn more that way. The second and last insight was that teachers should become role models. Aside from employing

engaging and interesting tasks, teachers must set a good example for the students to learn from. They should be wide readers, open-minded, and employ strategies for a better understanding of literary pieces. The teachers should become models worth emulating so that students can also be inspired in reading and learning.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the study participants, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of secondary male English teachers delve into the biases toward male English teachers, lack of learning resources, and students with

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. In the Philippines, literature was a compulsory subject in the general education curriculum of high school, which was embedded in their subjects. It was also taught at the senior high school level and in universities and colleges, particularly for those students who specialize in language and literature courses. Literature teaches students other skills, such as reading, writing, and speaking. Teaching literature is not only concerned with teaching students how to make literary interpretations and analyses but also helps students acquire and develop sensitivity, self-awareness, and a greater understanding of the world and other people. Literature was a giving tree. We could derive plenty of skills from reading and appreciating literature. However, it was not a paved road. Instead, it was a rough one. One must be passionate about learning it to derive something from it. A teacher's duty was to make sure students were getting and learning what they should be learning. Reading and teaching have been viewed as feminine activities and jobs since ancient times. Although society and its views have changed a lot, there are

4.3. Future Directions—

different levels of language proficiency. The secondary male English teachers' coping mechanisms included the resourcing strategy, the repeat or rereading strategy, and reading between the lines. The insights drawn from the findings of the study were: employing innovative learning tasks and teachers being role models as learners of literature.

still more female teachers. Hence, the study was intended to unfurl the literary appreciation experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of secondary male English teachers. The study discovered biases in male English teachers. There was also a lack of learning resources. Students with different levels of language proficiency are also present in the classrooms. This could serve as a roadblock because it could hinder the pace of the class, and the teacher's attention was more diverted to the students who needed assistance and guidance. In the midst of all these challenges and experiences, the teachers have devised coping mechanisms. For the lack of resources, they have utilized a resourcing strategy. They also used repeat reading and reading between the lines. The two insights drawn from the study were innovative learning tasks and teachers becoming role models. The first insight, employing innovative learning tasks, is targeted towards improving learning delivery and enriching the way students learn. The second and last insight is that teachers should become role models. Aside from employing engaging and interesting tasks, teachers must set a good example for the students to learn from.

Based on the study's findings, the findings must be properly relayed and used by the significant people for whom this research was intended. The educational leaders. They should be more aware of the teacher's experiences and challenges in literary appreciation. Once they can recognize and reflect on this existing scenario, such as the lack of learning resources, they can find a solution to this existing problem. Furthermore, the fundamental move educational leaders can provide is to generate strategies for teachers to supply to their students. Another would be to hold meetings aimed at improving the delivery of teaching literature compatible with the student's needs and interests. The school principals or school heads were more receptive to the current challenges of teachers in teaching literature and achieving literary appreciation. The school heads may further support the teachers by providing more resources in teaching literature so that they could offer students a variety of learning experiences about literature. They could also encourage the teachers to be more open about their thoughts and emotions so that the school could provide guidance and support. The learners. They are more engaged and proactive in learning literature and their other subjects. They may see the real-life impact and benefits that come with learning and appreciating literature. It entailed a lot of skills and abilities that were useful for their academic journey. Also, they were more appreciative of their teachers who exhaust all the best ways possible to teach them. Other stakeholders. They may provide support to better enhance the teaching-learning experience in teaching and achieving literary appreciation. The stakeholders may be the source of other ways and means to solve some of the challenges faced by teachers. Future researchers may conduct the study but take the perspective of the students. If the employed strategies are deemed effective in achieving literary appreciation and an in-depth understanding of the text, they may also explore different challenges and strategies to open new avenues to improve the way learners learn.

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